

**SCHOOL CLIMATE AND GENDER AS FACTORS IN RISKY SEXUAL BEHAVIOUR OF
ADOLESCENTS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with visual impairment has continued to be a source of concern to different tiers of government, parents, teachers and members of society at large. Several studies on adolescents with visual impairment have been on their academic achievement and the development of daily living skills with little or no studies devoted to their participation in risky sexual activities. This study, therefore, focused on school climate and gender as factors in risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with visual impairment in South western, Nigeria. The Health Belief Model and Social Learning Theory provided the framework for the study. A descriptive research design of correlational type was adopted using purposive sampling technique to select twelve integrated schools in six southwestern States (Ekiti-1, Lagos -4, Ogun -4, Ondo -1, Osun-1 and Oyo-1). Snellen's chart was used to screen adolescents with visual impairment to ascertain their visual acuity. Afterwards, a total enumeration of three hundred and eleven (311) adolescents with visual impairment was adopted. The average age of the respondents was + 17 years old. Data was collected through the school Climate Student Scale ($\alpha = .92$) and Adolescents Risky Behaviour Questionnaire ($\alpha = .73$). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and t-test. Findings showed that there was a significant relationship between school climate and risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with visual impairment. The study also revealed a significant gender difference in risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with visual impairment in Oyo State. Based on the findings, it was recommended that school administrators, special educators, and counsellors should help adolescents with visual impairments to recognise and appreciate the roles and impact of the school environment in shaping their lifestyles and dispositions towards reducing risky sexual behaviour. This help should go beyond the cognitive level change, individual values, and group norms to include building social skills.

Keywords: Visual Impairment; Risky Sexual Behaviour; School Climate; Adolescents

Introduction

Risky sexual behaviour can be defined as the engagement in activities that increase one's susceptibility to problems related to sexuality and reproductive health. Risky sexual behaviour includes having sex at a very tender age, having many sexual partners, engaging in prostitution, having sex while under the influence of alcohol or drugs and engaging in unprotected sexual activities. Risky sexual behavior becomes more problematic when viewed through the lenses of adolescents with disabilities, especially those with visual impairment who are often vulnerable and highly endangered. Adolescents and adults with disabilities constitute about 10% of the World's population (WHO) International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF, 2002). It is clear that little is known about how adolescents make choices to engage in or not to engage in sexual experience. Often researchers assume that, for adolescents, engaging in sexual intercourse is sexual risk-taking (Blum et al., 2000).

Adolescence is a transitional phase of growth and development between childhood and adulthood. An adolescent is any person between the ages of 10 and 23 years (WHO, 2002). However, different societies have different age grades, characteristics and responsibilities they assign to individuals within this transitional phase. The adolescent stage is a crucial stage in the development of an individual. Proper education, mentoring and parenting are thus required to enable an individual sail successfully through this stormy phase and become a mature and well-bred adult with focus and purpose in life. It behooves on parents, teachers and a host of many others in society to provide the needed examples and guidance to see children through the phase of adolescence. In a nutshell, the concept of adolescence is the notion of transition, a period of change, growth and disequilibrium.

Visual impairment is a significant limitation of visual capability resulting from disease, trauma, or congenital or degenerative conditions that cannot be corrected by conventional means such as refractive correction or medication. It is classified into partial sightedness, low vision and total blindness. Heward (2006) states that children with visual loss are those who, as a result of their limited or total loss of vision, are deficit in one or more skills requiring vision. As a result, they need special equipment and adaptations to function effectively at school and at home. It is well documented that adolescents with visual impairment engage in sexual activities with limited or inadequate information inherent in sexuality and reproductive health. In this connection, Katuta (2011) opines that the engagement of adolescents with visual impairments in harmful sexual conduct is due to accrued factors such as lack of information on the state and expression of "maleness" or "femaleness", physical susceptibility, the necessity for support and care, the need for guidance in moving around, life in institutions, and the seeming general assumption that individuals with visual impairment are not capable of being reliable witness for themselves, thus exposing them to abuse. Adolescents with visual impairment from poor households are particularly prone to sexual risk-taking, with their economic status motivating them to partake in transactional sex and serving as another limitation in their negotiating power with respect to safer sex practice (Kendi, Mweru & Kinai, 2012; Sithinyiwe & Ngonidzashe, 2016).

There are many misconceptions about the sexuality of adolescents with visual impairment and the most common is that they are asexual and as such, they do not need information about their sexuality. The needless misconceptions largely account for their potential physical, mental, and social risk as well as their inability to observe, develop and practice appropriate sexual behaviour. Despite the few studies on the different facets of sexuality of persons with visual impairment, available literature has been able to reveal some sexual activities and experiences of adolescents with disabilities in Nigeria and across the globe. For instance, a study conducted by Alamrew, Tareken, Alamirew and Asres (2014) on risky sexual behavior and its associated factors among people

with disabilities in Dessie, Ethiopia, revealed that 301 (73.1%) out of 412 respondents have had intercourse. Out of this number, 153 respondents (50.8%) were below the age of 18 years and the median age at sexual debut was 18 years. According to the findings of the study, 174 (57%) of them accepted to have had sex out of their own personal interest, 68 (22%) reported their own case as due to peer pressure and 3.7% was due to an economic problem. Similarly, a study conducted in Tanzania showed that almost half of the people with one disability or the other have had sex before the age of 19 (Margaret, Raphael & Herman, 2009).

It is pertinent to note that studies involving the association of school climate, gender and risky sex among adolescents with visual impairment have been quite scarce. Thus, the need for this present study became imperative and relevant. The study was anchored on the Health Belief Model (HBM) developed in 1950s but later refined by Rosenstock, Strecher and Becker in 1999 and Social Learning Theory propounded by Albert Bandura in 1977. The tenet of Health Belief Model (HBM) is that health behaviour is measured by personal beliefs or perception about a disease and the strategies available to decrease its occurrence and this model illuminates how adolescents view or perceive sex-related matters. The Social Learning Theory centres on the learning that occurs within a social environment and the belief is that people learn from one another through such concepts as observational learning, imitation and modelling. In addition, the following research questions were raised to guide the study; (1) What is the relationship between school climate and risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with visual impairment in South Western, Nigeria; (2) What is the significant gender difference in risky sexual behavior among adolescents with visual impairment in Southwestern, Nigeria?

Method

Descriptive survey research design was used to collect data for this study. This design was chosen because events had already occurred thereby making manipulation of variables unnecessary. The respondents for this study were 311 adolescents with visual impairment. Purposive sampling technique was used to select secondary schools (integrated settings) in Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo States in Southwestern, Nigeria. Snellen's chart was used to screen adolescents with visual impairment to really ascertain their visual acuity in the selected secondary schools in South-western, Nigeria.

Instrumentation

The following instruments were used to collect data: Adolescent Risky Behaviour Questionnaire (ARBQ) It was adapted from the Youth Risk Behaviour Surveillance System (YRBSS), developed in 1988 by the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDCP) to monitor health risk behaviour that contributes to the leading causes of mortality, morbidity, and social problems among youth and adults in the United States. The initial 13 items were subjected to validity and reliability tests through a pilot study in order to ascertain its suitability for the study. Critical reliability analysis of the original 13 items brought down the number to 9. Further reliability test of the 9 items was also carried out and the results indicated that the scale has a Cronbach's Alpha reliability of 0.73. This is adjudged to be reliable.

Snellen's Chart

The standard eye chart known as "Snellen Chart" was developed by Herman Snellen in the year 1862. It is a standardised eye screening test adopted by the World Health Organisation (WHO) to identify the degree of visual loss. It has a series of letters or letters and numbers, with the largest at the top. The letters have different sizes such that the top letters should be seen clearly by an eye with normal vision at a distance of 200ft or 60metres. Each row has a figure at the side indicating the distance in metres or feet at which that row can be seen by normal eyes. The letter *E' was used to screen the adolescents with visual impairment in order to ascertain their level of visual loss that is, whether it is low or total vision loss. School Climate Student Scale (SCSS): School climate

scale was adapted from the revised version of the Dimension of Excellence Scale (DOES) developed by Dusewicz and Beyer (2014). The DOES package is a set of survey instruments designed to be used with school staff, parents, and students to assess the quality and effectiveness of a local school or district. Each survey addresses dimensions found to be related to school effectiveness in a wide variety of educational research studies. The dimensions include school climate, leadership, teacher behaviour, curriculum, monitoring and assessment, student discipline and behaviour, staff development, and parent involvement. The present study adapted the school climate student dimension. The scale consists of 21 items to measure school climate on a five-point Likert format of 1-strongly agree to 5- strongly disagree. The instrument had reported an adequate reliability index of ($\alpha = .96$). However, further reliability was conducted through a pilot study and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.92 was obtained.

Procedure

Approval was sought from the appropriate authorities to conduct the study in the designated locations. The instruments were administered to all selected respondents after their willingness to participate has been obtained. The administration of the instruments lasted six weeks. One week was spent in the administration of the instruments in each state. The researcher engaged the services of four research assistants who were trained in order to facilitate the administration of the questionnaire. The respondents were informed about the study and their rights regarding participation. The researcher and the research assistants then administered the questionnaires which were read to them by sighted guides and encouraged the respondents to fill in their responses without prejudice. The copies of the questionnaires were collected on the spot. Method of Data Analysis The data collected were analysed using frequency count, percentages, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and T-test statistics.

Discussion

The current study examined the effect of school climate and gender on risky sexual behaviour of the adolescents with visual impairment in Southwestern, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised to guide the study. The first research question sought to find out the significant relationship existing between school climate and risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with visual impairment in Southwestern, Nigeria while the second research question attempted to determine the significant gender difference in risky sexual behaviour among adolescents with visual impairment in Southwestern, Nigeria. The finding revealed a significant positive relationship between school climate and risky sexual behavior among adolescents with visual impairment. This finding corroborates the submission of Gregory et al. (2010) who found that consistent enforcement of school discipline (structure) and availability of caring adults (support) was associated with school safety. Similarly, Klein, Cornell and Konold (2013) found that positive school climate was associated with lower student risk behaviour. Guo (2012) found that the teachers' work environment, which may be considered as an indicator of teachers' relationships with each other and school administrators, fully mediated the path from a whole school character intervention to school climate change. This indicates the critical foundational role of positive adult relationships for a positive school climate.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was recommended that school administrators, special educators, and counselors should enable adolescents with visual impairment to recognise and appreciate the roles and impact of the school environment in shaping their lifestyles and dispositions towards reducing risky sexual behaviour among them. This should go beyond the cognitive level change, individual values, and group norms to include building social skills. Similarly, the government should support schools and communities in formulating policies and implementing practices aimed at reducing the risky sexual behaviour, bringing back religious education in schools and addressing the problem of poverty, especially among female adolescents with visual impairment in the

communities. Sexuality education should be incorporated into the school curriculum so as to enable adolescents especially those with visual impairment to acquire the required knowledge about sexuality, which will enable them to have recourse to their emotion in taking sexual-related decisions. There is also a pressing need to train specialist teachers or facilitators and lecturers who are conversant with visual impairment and who can positively impact the lives of adolescents with visual impairment.

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